

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON FORCED DEGRADATION AND ITS REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AS A CRITICAL TOOL IN STABILITY TESTING AND METHOD DEVELOPMENT

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guidelines.

ABSTRACT

Forced degradation studies are frequently carried out in the early stages of the development of vaccine candidates in order to learn more about potential degradation routes, promote the development of analytical tools, find suitable stabilizers for vaccines, and determine the ideal storage conditions. Rarely, if ever, are there any procedural instructions on how to conduct forced degradation studies in the regulatory guidelines for forced degradation of biologics. In this article, we present a summary of the approaches utilized to investigate forced deterioration in vaccines, forced degradation instances were undertaken, along with mechanisms of degradation and analysis technique. for vaccination products, and an overview of stabilizers that are employed to affect the outcomes of new candidate vaccines.

KEYWORDS: Forced degradation studies, Degradation routes, Analytical tool, Storage conditions, Regulatory

INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of the biopharmaceutical sector within the pharmaceutical industry is largely driven by significant advancements in protein chemistry and modern biotechnological techniques, such as recombinant DNA and hybridoma technologies.^[1] At present, more than 900 protein-based therapeutics are in various stages of clinical development, while the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved over 150 peptides and proteins as therapeutic agents for the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of numerous diseases.^[2] Furthermore, there are currently 39 monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) in the late stages of phase III clinical trials, with four additional mAbs anticipated to be submitted for marketing approval by the end of 2015.^[3] The physicochemical complexity of biopharmaceuticals, which are large and structurally intricate molecules, is remarkably high.^[60] Such complex macromolecules, containing diverse functional groups, are inherently susceptible to instability through multiple degradation pathways. These degradative processes can be triggered by exposure to various environmental changes and stresses encountered during their multistep production, handling, shipping, storage, and even after administration to patients. The formation of degradation products represents a significant concern, as these by-products pose a major risk for immunogenic responses in patients, in addition to potentially compromising the therapeutic efficacy and potency of the biopharmaceutical product. Consequently, stability studies are considered one of the most critical aspects of quality control in the development and manufacturing of biopharmaceuticals.^[4,5]

Biopharmaceuticals primarily exhibit two categories of stability challenges: chemical and physical instability. Physical instability refers to alterations in the higher-order structures of proteins, such as deviations from their optimal transition (unfolding) temperature and changes in their native three-dimensional globular conformations. These alterations may manifest through processes such as unfolding, dissociation, denaturation, adsorption, aggregation, and precipitation—all of which contribute to the overall degradation of the biopharmaceutical product.^[6,7] To illustrate, the unfolding of proteins represents a significant form of physical instability, leading to disruptions in their tertiary and, in some cases, secondary structural arrangements. Such conformational alterations can compromise the biological functionality of biopharmaceuticals and may result in irreversible protein aggregation.^[8,9] While maintaining both physical and chemical stability is critical for ensuring the efficacy of biopharmaceutical products, these parameters alone are insufficient to guarantee their overall potency and safety. Therefore, a comprehensive stability assessment must also include the

evaluation of biological stability, which encompasses the ability of a biopharmaceutical to preserve its biological activity, potency, safety, and immunogenicity under various environmental conditions.^[10,11] In addition to real-time stability studies—commonly used to establish shelf life, expiration dates, and appropriate storage and handling conditions—stability studies under stress or forced degradation studies are equally essential. These studies are designed to simulate accidental or extreme conditions that a biopharmaceutical product might encounter during manufacturing, storage, handling, or administration. Forced degradation studies not only help demonstrate the robustness of bioassay methods used to assess potency but also provide valuable insights into the potential effects of specific degradation products on the toxicity and immunogenicity of biopharmaceutical formulations.^[12,13] In addition to employing reliable analytical techniques to monitor all potential degradation processes, the design of forced degradation studies requires careful selection of appropriate stress conditions based on the inherent instability pathways of the biopharmaceutical product. To obtain realistic degradation profiles, parameters such as stress type, exposure duration, target degradation level, and degradation limits must be carefully optimized. Overstressing may lead to excessive degradation and the formation of secondary degradation products that would not typically appear under real-time or accelerated stability conditions, while under stressing may result in insufficient degradation, limiting the usefulness of the study.^[14-17] The International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use provides key guidelines for conducting stability studies. The ICH Q1A(R2) guideline establishes a general framework for ensuring and evaluating the stability of pharmaceutical products,^[18] while ICH Q1B offers recommendations for conducting photostability testing of new drug substances and products, including advice on suitable light sources and control of light exposure levels.^[19] Furthermore, the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) has developed standards for vibration testing of shipping containers to evaluate the potential impact of transportation stress on product stability.^[20] It is generally recommended that stress conditions for biopharmaceuticals be determined on a case-by-case basis, as no universally standardized protocol currently exists for initiating stress testing of these complex molecules. Additionally, there are no well-established criteria for interpreting or evaluating the outcomes of such stress studies, further emphasizing the need for continued research and harmonization in this area.^[21]

❖ Importance of Forced Degradation Studies

Forced degradation studies play a crucial role in the development and quality assurance of biopharmaceutical products. These studies help in understanding the stability characteristics of drug substances and formulations under various stress conditions. The key reasons for conducting forced degradation studies include the following:

- **Resolution of stability-related issues:** Forced degradation helps identify and address stability problems that may arise during the product's lifecycle.
- **Development of more stable formulations:** Insights gained from these studies facilitate the design of formulations with enhanced stability.
- **Elucidation of degradation product structures:** They enable the identification and structural characterization of degradation products.
- **Establishment of degradation pathways:** These studies help determine the degradation mechanisms of both drug substances and drug products.
- **Confirmation of method specificity:** Forced degradation supports the development of **stability-indicating analytical methods**, ensuring that analytical techniques can accurately distinguish the active drug from its degradation products.
- **Determination of intrinsic stability:** They help assess the inherent stability of drug substances within a formulation.
- **Understanding of chemical characteristics:** Such studies provide valuable insights into the chemical behavior of drug molecules under different stress conditions.

Overall, forced degradation studies contribute to understanding degradation mechanisms such as hydrolysis, oxidation, photolysis, and thermolysis of drug substances and products, ensuring the robustness and reliability of pharmaceutical formulations.

❖ Methods of Forced Degradation

1. Hydrolytic Conditions

Hydrolysis is one of the most common chemical degradation processes that occurs across a wide pH range. In this reaction, drug molecules react with water (a solvolysis process), leading to the formation of degradation products with different chemical structures. Hydrolytic degradation can occur when water is present as a solvent or as atmospheric moisture in pharmaceutical dosage forms. For example, aspirin undergoes hydrolysis in the presence of water to yield salicylic acid and acetic acid.^[28,29] During hydrolytic stress studies, the catalysis of ionizable functional groups in the molecule is examined under both acidic and

basic conditions. Acidic and basic stress samples are typically prepared using hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH), respectively.^[30]

2. Oxidative Conditions

Oxidation is another major pathway for drug degradation. It can be induced by oxidizing agents such as metal ions, oxygen, or radical initiators (e.g., azobisisobutyronitrile, AIBN). Among these, hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is the most commonly used oxidizing agent in forced degradation studies.

The selection of the oxidizing agent, its concentration, and experimental conditions depend on the chemical nature of the drug substance. According to literature, exposure of drug solutions to 0.1–3% hydrogen peroxide for up to seven days at ambient temperature and neutral pH can yield degradation products of analytical relevance, typically achieving a maximum degradation of around 20%.^[31]

Oxidative degradation generally involves electron transfer reactions, forming reactive anions and cations. This process can generate N-oxides, hydroxylamines, sulphones, and sulphoxides from functional groups such as phenols, sulphides, and amines.^[32] Functional groups containing labile hydrogens, for example, those attached to benzylic, allylic, or tertiary carbons, or positioned α to a heteroatom are particularly prone to oxidation, forming products such as hydroperoxides, alcohols, or ketones.^[33,34]

3. Particle Size Analysis

The development and evaluation of vaccines require several analytical techniques to assess aggregation and particle size distribution. Controlling aggregation during the manufacturing process and storage period is a major challenge for many biopharmaceuticals. Regulatory agencies emphasize the importance of fully characterizing these parameters due to their potential impact on product safety, efficacy, and immunogenicity. It is well-documented that protein aggregates can exert undesirable effects, including unwanted immune responses that may compromise drug effectiveness.^[35] Therefore, a combination of analytical techniques is employed to effectively characterize particulate matter. Since no single method can adequately measure the full range of particle sizes from nanometres (e.g., protein aggregates) to micrometres and visible particles multiple orthogonal analytical techniques must be used. This ensures comprehensive coverage across the entire size spectrum and enables cross-validation of results for accuracy and reliability.^[36]

4. Freeze–Thaw Cycling

Freeze–thaw studies are conducted to evaluate the stability of vaccines under conditions involving low temperatures and ice–water interfaces, which can induce product instability. These studies are essential to identify suitable excipients that can stabilize the formulation during freezing, storage, or lyophilization, and to support the definition of acceptable temperature excursions during transportation and handling. Key parameters influencing freeze–thaw behaviour include the rate of freezing, sample concentration, and container geometry. The scale of the study must also be carefully considered, as freezing dynamics vary significantly between small and large volumes. For instance, small sample volumes (1–5 mL) typically freeze uniformly within a few minutes, whereas larger volumes (10 mL or more) may exhibit non-uniform freezing, leading to heterogeneity in protein concentration, pH, and osmolarity. Observations have shown that larger samples often display higher protein concentrations at the middle and bottom of the container following the freeze–thaw process.^[37]

5. Mechanical Stress

The design of mechanical stress studies depends on both the condition under investigation and the stage of product development. These studies help to understand how physical forces encountered during manufacturing, processing, and handling may affect product stability. Mechanical stress can result from operations such as mixing, pumping, agitation, or filling of the drug product. Such processes can induce shear stress, air–liquid interface exposure, or cavitation, potentially leading to protein unfolding, aggregation, or loss of biological activity. The experimental parameters—such as mixing speed, duration, or pumping rate—should be selected to accurately reflect the actual manufacturing conditions of the formulation being studied. Appropriate design of mechanical stress testing ensures that any degradation observed is representative of real-world handling and production processes.^[38]

6. Light Stress

Light stress studies are performed to evaluate the susceptibility of vaccines to photodegradation, which may occur during manufacturing, storage, transportation, or administration. Vaccines may be exposed to sunlight or artificial light sources, both of which can initiate photochemical reactions that compromise product stability. To mitigate these risks, most marketed vaccines include the label warning “Protect from direct light”, and are packaged in light-protective secondary containers. The extent and rate of light-induced

degradation depend on several factors, including the composition of the product, the nature of the viral or protein structure, the wavelength and intensity of light, and the duration of exposure. Certain amino acid residues, such as cysteine (Cys), tryptophan (Trp), tyrosine (Tyr), and phenylalanine (Phe), are particularly sensitive to photodegradation. Exposure to light can lead to covalent modifications or the formation of cross-links between protein molecules, promoting the development of higher-order aggregates that may negatively impact vaccine efficacy and safety.^[39]

Forced Degradation Studies fig. 1.

❖ Regulatory Guidelines on Forced Degradation and Stability Testing

1. ICH Guidelines (International Council for Harmonisation)

- **ICH Q1A (R2)** – Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products (Stress Testing): Recommends performing forced degradation studies to understand the chemical behavior of drug substances and products under stress conditions, including oxidation, photolysis, and elevated temperatures (>50°C). Testing should cover a wide pH range for solutions/suspensions. Data obtained help in developing stability-indicating analytical methods.^[40]
- **ICH Q1B**– Photostability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products: Provides methodologies for assessing photostability of active ingredients and finished products. Forced degradation is performed under light exposure on different forms (solid, solution, suspension). Degradation products formed only during forced testing but not in actual stability studies need not be further evaluated.^[14]

- **ICH Q2B (Now ICH Q2(R2))** – Validation of Analytical Procedures: Methodology: Emphasizes the importance of specificity, particularly demonstrated through forced degradation samples. Specificity ensures the analytical method can accurately measure analyte response without interference from degradation products or impurities.^[42]
- **ICH Q3A (R2)**– Impurities in New Drug Substances: Outlines requirements for identification, classification, and reporting of impurities. Both chemical and safety perspectives are considered, including impurities found at low levels in the new drug substance.^[43]

2. EMA Guidelines (European Medicines Agency)

- According to the EMA document “*Requirements to the Chemical and Pharmaceutical Quality Documentation Concerning Investigational Medicinal Products in Clinical Trials*”, details on critical stability parameters (e.g., photosensitivity, hygroscopicity) and potential degradation pathways must be presented.^[44]
- The guideline “*Stability Testing for Applications for Variations to a Marketing Authorization*” highlights that the extent of stability studies should depend on prior knowledge of the active substance’s stability profile, including any available stress testing data.^[45]

3. FDA Guidelines (U.S. Food and Drug Administration)

Forced degradation testing is described as purposeful degradation conducted primarily during development to^[46]

- Understand degradation pathways.
- Assess photosensitivity and chemical stability.
- Aid in developing stability-indicating methods.

The FDA differentiates between forced degradation (developmental) and confirmatory stability testing (regulatory). Degradation products unique to forced testing need not be pursued further. Specificity should be validated to ensure no interference among drug, degradants, impurities, excipients, or container systems. Comprehensive documentation is required to justify the extent and rationale of forced degradation studies.^[47]

4. USP Pharmacopoeia (United States Pharmacopeia)

When impurity or degradation standards are unavailable, specificity can be demonstrated by comparing results with a second validated method (e.g., pharmacopeial procedure). Stress conditions such as light, heat, humidity, acid/base hydrolysis, and oxidation should be tested, and chromatographic impurity profiles compared for consistency.^[48]

5. JP Pharmacopoeia (Japanese Pharmacopoeia)

The specificity of an analytical method must be demonstrated, typically by comparing results from pure analyte samples with those containing excipients, related substances, or degradation products. In absence of impurity standards, samples from accelerated or stress studies may be used to confirm method performance.^[49]

6. ANVISA Guidelines (Brazil – National Health Surveillance Agency)

Established under Law No. 9782/1999, ANVISA regulates pharmaceuticals to protect and promote public health in Brazil. Its role encompasses monitoring product quality, safety, and efficacy, in alignment with Brazil's Unified Health System (SUS). Forced degradation and stability testing fall under its broader mandate to control risks related to pharmaceutical manufacturing and use.^[50]

❖ STABILITY INDICATING METHODS

A Stability Indicating Method (SIM) is an analytical technique employed to measure the decrease in the quantity of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) in a drug product due to degradation. According to an FDA guidance document, a stability-indicating method is a validated quantitative analytical process that tracks the changes in drug ingredients and drug product stability over time. This method accurately assesses fluctuations in the concentration of the active component without being influenced by additional degradation products, impurities, or excipients.^[51] Stress tests are performed to demonstrate the method's specificity in detecting alterations in the concentration of the drug substance, particularly in situations where limited data on potential degradation products are available. The establishment of an effective stability indicating method serves as a crucial foundation for pre-formulation investigations, stability studies, and the establishment of suitable storage conditions.^[52] stability suggesting analytical techniques have been explored from a regulatory perspective. A UV detector is most typically used in conjunction with the RP-HPLC, a widely used analytical instrument for separating and measuring contaminants.^[53]

Described as "a validated quantitative analytical method that can detect changes in the chemical, physical, or microbiological properties of the drug substance and drug product over time, and that is specific enough that the active ingredient and degradation product content can be accurately measured without interference," the stability indicating method is used to determine the stability of pharmaceutical products.^[54,55] As per the guidelines of the US Food and Drug Administration (USFDA), a Stability Indicating Assay Method (SIAM) is a validated analytical approach that precisely and accurately quantifies active ingredients (whether in drug substance or drug product form) without being influenced by potential interferences such as degradation products, process impurities, excipients, or other potential impurities. The FDA emphasizes that all testing methods utilized in stability evaluations should be capable of indicating stability.

A SIAM, a quantitative analytical technique, is used to identify an active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) reduction caused by deterioration. SIAM is commonly used in the pharmaceutical sector to analyze stability sample data.^[56,57] The first step in developing a method is determining the pKa value, log P, solubility, and composition of the required drug.

It is common practice to create a reverse phase HPLC method for pharmaceutical separation. Methanol, acetonitrile, and water, among other commonly used solvents, are used as mobile phases in various ratios and combinations. The organic phase, such as acetonitrile or methanol, is chosen based on the drug's solubility profile. Earlier reports or techniques based on trial and error are often used to select the mobile phase and its proportion. The organic and aqueous phases are kept at a 50:50 ratio at the start of the experiment, and the solvent ratios for the mobile phase can be further optimized to offer the best results.^[58]

1. Understand the physicochemical properties and chemistry of the drug

During drug stability studies, the experimental conditions are established based on the physicochemical properties of the Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API). These properties include the dissociation constant, partition coefficients, fluorescent characteristics, chromatographic behaviour, oxidation-reduction potentials, and spectrophotometric properties. Understanding these attributes is vital for ensuring appropriate experimental settings and conditions during drug stability investigations.^[59]

2. Set up preliminary HPLC condition

For the selection of preliminary experimental conditions for stability studies, a literature search and an official or non-official technique are commonly used. The experimental circumstances are chosen based on the API properties.^[60]

3. Sample preparation for method development

Stability indicating methods are established by stressing the API under accelerated conditions to degrade the API up to 5-10%, which is then analyzed using the appropriate preliminary HPLC condition and detector.^[61]

4. Develop Stability indicating chromatographic conditions

The flow mode, solvent types, mobile phase, pH, type of column, and temperature are common separation variables.^[62]

5. Method of Optimization

After obtaining the proper separation, the experimental conditions should be tweaked to obtain the desired separation and sensitivity. PH (ionic), mobile phase component and ratio, gradient, flow rate, temperature, injections volume, and diluents sample type should all be thoroughly examined to establish the experimental conditions.^[63]

6. Validation of Analytical Method

According to the ICH/USP recommendations, analytical procedures must be validated. If degradation products are present in quantities greater than the identification threshold (about 0.1%), they must be isolated, identified, characterized, and qualified.⁹ Validation includes checking the method's robustness, ruggedness, linearity, range, specificity, limit of detection, and limit of quantitation.^[64]

❖ INSTRUMENTS USED IN FORCE DEGRADATION STUDIES

HPLC: High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) plays a crucial role in both the pharmaceutical and chemical sectors, particularly in the context of forced degradation studies. These studies are designed to evaluate how pharmaceutical compounds withstand different stress conditions, including variations in temperature, humidity, exposure to light, and contact with acidic or alkaline environments, providing essential insights into their stability and degradation. HPLC plays a crucial role in these studies by allowing scientists to

monitor and quantify the degradation products and determine the stability of the drug substance or drug product. Here's how HPLC is used in force degradation studies:

- **Quantification of degradation products:** HPLC is employed to separate and quantify the degradation products that may form during the force degradation study. The chromatographic separation enables the identification and quantification of impurities and degradation products, providing critical information on the compound's stability.
- **Monitoring degradation kinetics:** HPLC can be used to track the degradation of the pharmaceutical compound over time. By analyzing multiple samples taken at different time points during the study, researchers can establish the rate at which degradation occurs and predict the compound's shelf life under various storage conditions.
- **Method development and validation:** Scientists develop and validate specific HPLC methods tailored to the compound being studied. These methods must be sensitive, selective, and reproducible to accurately detect and quantify degradation products. Validation ensures that the HPLC method meets regulatory requirements for accuracy and precision.
- **Forced degradation conditions:** HPLC is instrumental in evaluating the impact of various stress conditions on the compound's stability. For example, samples subjected to high temperature, humidity, or exposure to light can be analyzed using HPLC to detect and quantify degradation products, helping to identify the most significant degradation pathways.
- **Structural elucidation:** HPLC can be coupled with other analytical techniques such as mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS) or nuclear magnetic resonance (HPLC-NMR) to further elucidate the structures of degradation products. This is essential for understanding the mechanisms of degradation and identifying potential toxic or impurity-forming pathways.
- **Stability-indicating method:** HPLC methods developed for force degradation studies are often stability-indicating. This means that they can differentiate between the active pharmaceutical ingredient and its degradation products, ensuring that the analytical method is specific to the compound of interest.
- **Regulatory compliance:** Regulatory agencies require pharmaceutical companies to conduct force degradation studies as part of the drug development process. HPLC data, including chromatograms and quantitative results, are typically included in regulatory submissions to demonstrate the compound's stability and safety. In summary, HPLC is an invaluable tool in force degradation studies, as it enables the quantitative analysis of

degradation products, monitors degradation kinetics, and aids in the development of stability-indicating methods.

This information is crucial for ensuring the safety, efficacy, and quality of pharmaceutical products.^[65]

Ultraviolet (UV): UV spectroscopy is another important analytical technique commonly used in force degradation studies, particularly in the pharmaceutical and chemical industries. UV spectroscopy entails measuring the absorption of ultraviolet light by a substance, and it is a valuable tool for assessing the stability and degradation of compounds. In the context of forced degradation studies, UV spectroscopy is used to identify chromophores within the sample.

Many organic compounds, including pharmaceuticals, possess chromophores - chemical groups that absorb UV light at specific wavelengths. By analyzing the UV absorption spectrum of a compound, researchers can identify the presence of chromophores, which are often associated with functional groups susceptible to degradation. This helps in predicting potential degradation pathways. Quantification of Impurities and Degradation Products: UV spectroscopy can be used to quantify impurities and degradation products formed during force degradation studies. Each compound typically has a characteristic absorption maximum (λ_{max}) at a specific wavelength.

Monitoring changes in absorbance at the λ_{max} can provide quantitative data on the extent of degradation and impurity formation.

Stability Indicating Method: UV methods can be developed and validated as stability-indicating methods. These methods are specific to the compound of interest and can differentiate between the parent compound and its degradation products. They are essential for ensuring the reliability of stability testing results. **Determination of Degradation Kinetics:** UV spectroscopy can be used to study the kinetics of degradation reactions. By measuring absorbance at specific time intervals under various stress conditions, researchers can determine reaction rates, order of reaction, and activation energies, providing insights into the stability of the compound. **Monitoring Changes in Concentration:** UV spectroscopy can track changes in the concentration of the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) over time. This is critical for assessing the shelf life and stability of a drug product under different storage

conditions. Method Validation: UV methods used in force degradation studies must be validated to ensure their accuracy, precision, specificity, and robustness. Validation is necessary for compliance with regulatory requirements. Comparative Analysis: UV spectroscopy can be used to compare the stability of a compound under different stress conditions. For example, it can help determine whether a drug product is more stable under dry or humid conditions, or whether exposure to light accelerates degradation. Structural Changes: UV spectroscopy can provide insights into structural changes that may occur during degradation. Shifts in absorption maxima or changes in the shape of the UV spectrum can indicate alterations in the compound's chemical structure. In summary, UV spectroscopy is a valuable analytical tool in force degradation studies because it enables the identification of chromophores, quantification of impurities, determination of degradation kinetics, and the development of stability-indicating methods. It plays a crucial role in assessing the stability and safety of pharmaceutical compounds and helps ensure regulatory compliance.^[66]

❖ ACID AND BASE DEGRADATION

Regarding acid degradation, sample solution A was mixed at room temperature for a short while before being immediately mixed with 5 mL of 5N HCl and 5 mL of 5N NaOH (for a 0hr sample).

For sample collection after 24 hours, sample solution A containing 5 mL of 5N HCl was maintained at room temperature for 24 hours before 5N NaOH was added. With regard to base degradation, sample solution A was equilibrated at room temperature, and then 5 mL of 2N NaOH and 5 mL of 2N HCl were added right away to neutralize the solution.

This was diluted to the desired strength and allowed to sit for 15 minutes (one hour sample). Added 5 mL of sample solution A after keeping it at room temperature for 24 hours.^[67,68] Hydrolytic stress testing, involving acid and base conditions for drug compounds and drug products in solution, can be conducted at either ambient temperature or elevated temperatures. The selection of the specific acid or base and their concentrations is determined by the stability characteristics of the pharmaceutical substance. During the testing, the drug substance solution is exposed to varying pH levels, such as 2, 7, and 10-12, at room temperature for a duration of two weeks, with a permissible maximum degradation of 15%. Appropriate reagents for hydrolysis include sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide

(ranging from 0.1 M to 1 M) for acid hydrolysis, and hydrochloric acid or sulfuric acid (ranging from 0.1 M to 1 M) for base hydrolysis.^[69]

Understanding the properties of a substance is crucial in determining the appropriate stress conditions. For instance, if a compound contains an ester functionality and is highly susceptible to base hydrolysis, minimal amounts of a base should be used. According to Figure 2, for investigating the hydrolytic degradation of a new drug with unknown stability characteristics, it is recommended to initiate the process by refluxing the drug in 0.1N HCl/NaOH for 8 hours, assuming the drug is sensitive. If a noticeable degradation occurs during this treatment, further tests are unnecessary. However, if no degradation is observed, the drug should be subjected to a 12-hour reflux in 1N acid/alkali. For drugs capable of withstanding more extreme acidic or alkaline conditions, additional tests, such as refluxing in 2N HCl/NaOH for 24 hours, can be conducted. Monitoring the reactions is essential, and if no significant changes are detected, the drug may be subjected to refluxing in 5N HCl/NaOH for a maximum of 24 hours. If no hydrolytic products are generated after treating the medicine to this rigorous condition, it may be called "practically stable." Returning to the beginning.^[70,71]

To begin stress testing under neutral conditions, the medication can be refluxed in water for 12 hours (Fig. 3). If no deterioration is observed, the refluxing period should be increased to one day. If no change is detected, it should be extended to two days. In the event of minor deterioration, the medicine may be refluxed for 5 days. If the medicine is still determined to be stable under neutral conditions, it may be declared non-degrading. For this investigation, it may be best to start with a sufficient amount of solution so that the time period can be gradually expanded as needed, without having to restart the reaction.

For a medication that is completely degraded during Pathway of Acid and Base Degradation Study for Drug Substance and Drug Product refluxing.^[72] By refluxing a new medicine in 0.1 N HCl / 0.1 N NaOH, the hydrolytic breakdown of the drug in acidic and alkaline conditions can be examined. If there is reasonable decline, testing can be terminated at this stage. If no degradation occurs under these conditions, the medicine should be refluxed in a stronger acid/alkali for a longer period of time.

FORCED DEGRADATION EXAMPLE OF DRUG

Fig. 2: Forced Degradation Example of Drug.

APPLICATION OF FORCED DEGRADATION

1. Pharmaceuticals

- **Stability Testing:** Forced degradation studies help pharmaceutical companies determine the shelf life of a drug product by subjecting it to accelerated degradation conditions, such as elevated temperature, humidity, and exposure to light.
- **Identification of Degradation Products:** It helps identify and characterize degradation products that might form during storage or use, ensuring the safety and efficacy of the drug.
- **Impurity Profiling:** Forced degradation can reveal impurities and degradation pathways, leading to adjustments in the manufacturing process to minimize impurity formation.

2. Chemical Industry

- **Material Testing:** Forced degradation is used to assess the durability and performance of materials, such as polymers, coatings, and composites, under extreme conditions, including temperature, radiation, and chemical exposure.
- **Product Development:** In the development of chemical products like adhesives, paints, and lubricants, forced degradation helps determine their stability and potential failure modes.

3. Food and Beverage Industry

- **Product Shelf-Life Evaluation:** Forced degradation studies are conducted on food and beverage products to assess their stability and shelf life under various environmental conditions.
 - **Identification of Spoilage Products:** By subjecting food items to extreme conditions, researchers can identify potential spoilage compounds and develop strategies to prevent their formation.
4. Environmental Monitoring:
- **Pollutant Degradation:** Forced degradation can simulate the breakdown of pollutants and contaminants in the environment, helping to develop remediation strategies and assess the environmental impact of chemicals.

4. Polymer Industry

- **Polymer Aging:** Forced degradation can simulate the effects of long-term exposure to environmental factors on polymers, aiding in the design of more durable materials.

5. Electronics Industry

- **Electronic Component Testing:** Forced degradation is used to evaluate the reliability and lifetime of electronic components like semiconductors and capacitors by subjecting them to extreme conditions.

6. Cosmetic Industry

- **Cosmetic Product Stability:** Forced degradation studies are conducted to assess the stability of cosmetic products, ensuring that they maintain their intended properties over time.

7. Fuel and Energy Sector

- **Fuel Stability Testing:** Forced degradation is applied to assess the stability and degradation of fuels, such as gasoline and diesel, under various conditions to prevent engine problems and improve fuel quality.

In all these applications, forced degradation studies provide valuable insights into the behavior of substances and materials under stress, helping industries optimize processes, ensure product safety and efficacy, and meet regulatory requirements.^[73]

ADVANTAGES OF FORCED DEGRADATION

Stability Assessment: Forced degradation allows for the accelerated assessment of a substance's stability over time. This is particularly important in industries like pharmaceuticals and food, where product shelf life is a critical factor.

- **Impurity Identification:** Forced degradation helps identify and characterize degradation products and impurities that may form during storage, manufacturing, or use. This information is vital for ensuring product quality and safety.
- **Degradation Pathway Understanding:** It provides insights into the pathways by which a substance degrades. Understanding these pathways can lead to better control of manufacturing processes and the development of strategies to mitigate degradation.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Many regulatory authorities, such as the FDA in the United States and the EMA in Europe, require forced degradation studies as part of the drug approval process. Complying with these regulations is essential for getting products to market.
- **Product Development:** In industries like chemicals and materials, forced degradation helps in the development of more robust and durable products by identifying weaknesses and failure modes.
- **Safety Assurance:** For pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and food products, forced degradation studies help ensure that potential degradation products do not pose health risks to consumers.
- **Optimized Formulation:** By understanding how a product degrades under various conditions, manufacturers can optimize the formulation to improve stability and shelf life.
- **Environmental Impact Assessment:** In environmental studies, forced degradation can simulate the breakdown of pollutants and contaminants, helping assess the potential environmental impact of chemicals.
- **Predictive Modeling:** Data from forced degradation studies can be used to create predictive models that estimate a substance's stability under various conditions without the need for extended real-time testing.
- **Cost and Time Savings:** Accelerated degradation studies save time and resources compared to waiting for natural degradation to occur, allowing companies to bring products to market more quickly.
- **Quality Control:** Forced degradation can be used as a quality control tool to monitor and ensure the stability of products in storage or on the market.

- **Research and Development:** Researchers can use forced degradation to study the behavior of substances under extreme conditions, gaining insights into chemical reactions and degradation mechanisms.
- **Risk Mitigation:** By identifying potential degradation pathways and impurities, forced degradation studies help companies proactively mitigate risks associated with product degradation.^[74]

DISADVANTAGES OF FORCED DEGRADATION

- **Cost and Time-Consuming:** Forced degradation studies can be resource-intensive in terms of time, personnel, and equipment. Conducting a comprehensive study may require a significant investment.
- **Generation of Hazardous Substances:** Some stress conditions used in forced degradation studies, such as high temperature, light exposure, and acidic or alkaline conditions, can produce hazardous or toxic degradation products, which need to be handled and disposed of carefully.
- **Lack of Real-World Relevance:** The extreme stress conditions applied in forced degradation studies may not always reflect real-world storage and usage conditions. Therefore, the relevance of the generated degradation data to actual stability under typical storage conditions may be limited.
- **Difficulty in Identifying All Degradation Products:** It can be challenging to identify and characterize all degradation products accurately, especially if they are present in trace amounts or are structurally complex. This can lead to incomplete understanding of the degradation pathways.
- **Interpretation and Assessment:** Interpreting the significance of certain degradation products and understanding their potential impact on product safety and efficacy can be complex. Some degradation products may be harmless, while others could be toxic or have adverse effects.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** Forced degradation studies are often required by regulatory agencies to assess the stability of pharmaceuticals and ensure product safety and efficacy. However, compliance with these regulatory requirements can be burdensome and may require additional documentation and reporting.
- **Variability in Results:** Forced degradation studies may yield variable results depending on factors such as the choice of stress conditions, sample preparation, and analytical

methods used. This variability can make it challenging to draw definitive conclusions about the stability of a product.

- **Ethical Considerations:** In some cases, conducting forced degradation studies may raise ethical concerns, especially when dealing with expensive or limited-supply drugs or substances. The destruction of valuable or rare materials can be a drawback.
- **Environmental Impact:** The disposal of chemicals used in forced degradation studies, as well as the potential release of hazardous substances, can have adverse environmental impacts if not managed properly.
- **Limited Predictive Value:** While forced degradation studies can provide insights into potential degradation pathways, they may not always predict long-term stability accurately. Actual product stability can depend on a range of factors beyond what is assessed in these studies.^[75]

CONCLUSION

Forced degradation studies are a crucial part of drug development, as they provide valuable insights into the potential degradation pathways and products of active ingredients. These studies help us understand how a drug substance may break down under various conditions, shedding light on the structure of degradation products. While the degradation products generated in these studies may not always be formed under typical storage conditions, they play a vital role in developing stability-indicating methods for quality control.

Initiating degradation studies at the initial stages of drug development is advantageous as it enables researchers to acquire extensive insights into the molecule's stability progression. This data can then be utilized to enhance formulation and manufacturing procedures, as well as establish suitable storage conditions to preserve the drug's quality and effectiveness. It's important to note that there is no one-size-fits-all set of conditions for forced degradation studies, and regulatory guidance typically doesn't specify the exact conditions to be used.

Therefore, experimenters need to exercise common sense and choose conditions that are relevant and appropriate for the specific drug product or substance under investigation.

REFERENCES

1. G. Zhang, Mammalian cell culture for biopharmaceutical production, in: R.H. Baltz, J.E. Davies, A.L. Dermain (Eds.), Manual of Industrial Microbiology and Biotechnology, third ed., ASM Press, Washington, DC, 2010; 157.

2. M.A. Alsenaidy, N.K. Jain, J.H. Kim, C.R. Middaugh, D.B. Volkin, Protein comparability assessments and potential applicability of high throughput biophysical methods and data visualization tools to compare physical stability profiles, *Front. Pharmacol.*, 2014; 5: 39.
3. J.M. Reichert, Antibodies to watch in 2015, *MABs*, 2015; 7: 1–8.
4. A.L. Daugherty, R.J. Mersny, Formulation and delivery issues for monoclonal antibody therapeutics, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.*, 2006; 58: 686–706.
5. V. Filipe, A. Hawe, J.F. Carpenter, W. Jiskoot, Analytical approaches to assess the degradation of therapeutic proteins, *TRAC – Trends Anal. Chem.*, 2013; 49: 118–125.
6. W. Wang, Instability, stabilization and formulation of liquid protein pharmaceuticals, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1999; 185: 129–188.
7. J.L.E. Reubsæet, J.H. Beijnen, A. Bult, R.J. Maanen, J.A.D. Marchal, W.J.M. Underberg, Analytical techniques used to study the degradation of proteins and peptides: physical instability, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 1998; 17: 979–984.
8. P. Arora, R. Gandhi, T. Kelly, Overview of Drug Development for Protein Therapeutics: Present Strategies and Future Perspectives, *American Pharmaceutical Review*, 2011.
9. J.M.A. Gavina, P. Britz-McKibbin, Protein unfolding and conformational studies by capillary electrophoresis, *Curr. Anal. Chem.*, 2007; 3: 17–31.
10. ICH, International Conference on Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, Topic Q5C: Stability Testing of Biotechnological/Biological Products, Geneva, 1995. (accessed September 2015)
11. W. Wang, Potency Testing of Biopharmaceuticals, *American Pharmaceutical Review*, The Review of American Pharmaceutical Technology & Business, 2014.
12. K.B. Ajay, Stability of therapeutic peptides and proteins, in: A.K. Banga (Ed.), *Therapeutic Peptides and Proteins: Formulation, Processing, and Delivery Systems*, second ed., CRC, Boca Raton, 2006; 67–83.
13. M.S. Hora, B.L. Chen, Stabilization of biopharmaceutical products and finish product formulations, in: G. Walsh, B. Murphy (Eds.), *Biopharmaceuticals: An Industrial Perspective*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1999; 218–225.
14. M. Blessy, R.D. Patel, P.N. Prajapati, Y.K. Agrawal, Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs – a review, *J. Pharm. Anal.*, 2014; 4: 159–165.
15. S.R.J. Hicks, Forced Degradation to Develop Stability-indicating Methods, vol. 13, *Pharm. Outsourcing*, 2012.

16. ICH, International Conference on Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, Topic Q1A (R2): Stability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products, 2003.
17. ICH, International Conference on Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, Topic Q1B: Stability Testing: Photostability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products, 1996.
18. ASTM, The American Society for Testing Materials, Designation: D 999-01: Standard Test Methods for Vibration Testing of Shipping Containers, 2007.
19. M. Hashija, L. Li, N. Rahman, S.F. Ausar, Force degradation studies: an essential tool for the formulation and development of vaccines, *Vaccine*, 2013; 3: 11–33.
20. Bakshi M, Singh S. Development of validated stability-indicating assay methods—critical review. *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal*, 2002; 28(6): 1011-40.
21. Maheswaran R. FDA perspectives-scientific considerations of forced degradation studies in ANDA submissions. *Pharm. Technol.*, 2012; 36(5): 73.
22. Schmidt AS. Forced degradation studies for biopharmaceuticals. *BioPharm Int.*, 2016; 29(7): 24-9
23. Von V, Helene J, Aus S. Forced degradation studies - comparison between ICH, EMA, FDA and WHO guidelines and ANVISA's resolution RDC 53/2015; 2015.
24. Rawat T, Pandey IP. Forced degradation studies for drug substances and drug products - scientific and regulatory considerations. *J Pharm Sci Res.*, 2015; 7: 238-41.
25. Blessy M, Patel RD, Prajapati PN, Agarwal YK. Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs - a review. *J Pharm Anal*, 2014; 4: 159-65.
26. Qiu F Norwood DL, Identification of pharmaceutical impurities. *J Liq Chromatogr R T.*, 2007; 30: 877-935
27. Kovarikova P, Jiri K, Jiri D, Lucie T. HPLC study of glimepiride under hydrolytic stress conditions. *J. Pharmaceut Biomed*, 2004; 36: 205-209.
28. Singh S, Bakshi M. Guidance on conduct of stress tests to determine inherent stability of drugs. *Phrama Tech*, 2000; 24: 1-14.
29. K.M Alsante, A. Ando, R. Brown, et al., The role of degradant profiling in inactive pharmaceutical ingredients and drug products, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.*, 2007; 59(1): 29–37.
30. A. Gupta, J.S. Yadav, S. Rawat, et al., Method development and hydrolytic degradation study of Doxofylline by RPHPLC and LC– MS/MS, *Asian J. Pharm. Anal*, 2011; 1: 14–18.

31. G. Boccardi, Oxidative susceptibility testing, in: S.W. Baertschi (Ed.), *Pharmaceutical Stress Testing-Predicting Drug Degradation*, Taylor and Francis, New York, 2005; 220.
32. K.M. Alsante, T.D. Hatajik, L.L. Lohr, et al., Solving impurity/ degradation problems: case studies, in: S. Ahuja, K.M. Alsante (Eds.), *Handbook of Isolation and Characterization of Impurities in Pharmaceutical*, Academic Press, New York, 2003; 380.
33. Rosenberg AS. Effects of protein aggregates: an immunologic perspective. *AAPS J.*, 2006; 8(3): E501–E507.
34. EMEA. Production and Quality Control of Monoclonal Antibodies and Related Substances. [EMA/CHMP/BWP/15763/2007], 2007.
35. Kolhe P, Badkar A. Protein and solute distribution in drug substance containers during frozen storage and post-thawing: a tool to understand and define freezing-thawing parameters in biotechnology process development. *Biotechnol Prog.*, 2011; 27(2): 494–504.
36. Eppler A, Weigandt M, Hanefeld A, Bunjes H. Relevant shaking stress conditions for antibody preformulation development. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.*, 2010; 74(2): 139–147.
37. Kerwin BA, Remmele RL Jr. Protect from light: photodegradation and protein biologics. *J Pharm Sci.*, 2007; 96(6): 1468–1479.
38. Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (US) (1996) Guidance for industry Q1B photo stability testing of new drug substances and products in U.S. Dept of Health and Human Services. Food and Drug Administration Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research, Rockville, MD, 11-15.
39. ICH (2003) Stability testing of new drug substances and products Q1A (R2), IFPMA, Geneva, Switzerland.
40. ICH (1996) Impurities in new drug products, IFPMA, Geneva, Switzerland.
41. ICH Q3C (R3) (2002) Impurities: Guidelines for Residual solvents (Step 5), International Conference on Harmonization.
42. Guideline on the Requirements to the Chemical and Pharmaceutical Quality Documentation Concerning Investigational Medicinal Products in Clinical Trials, CHMP/QWP/185401/2004.
http://ec.europa.eu/health/files/eudralex/vol10/18540104en_en.pdf (assessed in February 2016)
43. Guideline on Stability Testing for Applications for Variations to a Marketing Authorization, EMA/CHMP/CVMP/QWP/441071-Rev.2, 21 March 2014.

- http://www.ema.europa.eu/docs/en_GB/document_library/Scientific_guideline/2014/04/W_C500164972.pdf (assessed in February 2016).
44. Guidance for Industry; Q1B Photostability Testing of New Drug Substances and Products.
<http://www.fda.gov/downloads/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/ucm073373.pdf> (assessed in February 2016)
45. Questions and Answers on Current Good Manufacturing Practices, Good Guidance Practices, Level 2 Guidance Laboratory Controls. <http://www.fda.gov/drugs/guidancecompliance/regulatoryinformation/guidances/ucm124785.htm> (assessed in February 2016)
46. United States Pharmacopeia, USP 38-NF 33, 2015. <http://www.usp.org/> (assessed in March 2016).
47. JP XVI; page 2149. <http://www.pmda.go.jp/files/000152816.pdf> (assessed in February 2016).
48. Homepage Anvisa. <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/wps/portal/anvisa-ingles> (assessed in March 2016).
49. FDA Guidance for Industry, Analytical Procedures and Methods Validation: Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls Documentation, Draft Guidance, Food and Drug Administration. Available from: (<http://www.fda.gov/downloads/Drugs/.../Guidances/ucm122858.pdf>), 2000.
50. M. Bakshi, S. Singh, Development of validated stability-indicating assay methods—critical review, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2002; 28(6): 1011–1040.
51. F. Qiu, D.L. Norwood, Identification of pharmaceutical impurities, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol.*, 2007; 30: 877–935.
52. Gupta A, Yadav JS, Rawat S (2011). Method development and hydrolytic degradation study of Doxofylline by RP HPLC and LC–MS/MS. *Asian J. Pharm. Anal*, 1: 14- 18.
53. Boccardi G, Baertschi SW (2005). Oxidative susceptibility testing. *Pharmaceutical Stress Testing Predicting Drug Degradation*. Taylor and Francis, New York, 220.
54. Snyder LR, Glajch JL, Kirkland JJ (1997). *Practical HPLC Method Development*. 2nd ed., Wiley, New York.
55. Riddhiben MP, Piyushbhai MP, Natubhai MP (2011). Stability indicating HPLC method development—a review. *Int. Res. J. Pharm.*, 2: 79-87.
56. Blessy MR, Patel RD, Prajapati PN, Agrawal YK. Development of forced degradation and stability indicating studies of drugs-A review. *Journal of pharmaceutical analysis*, Jun. 1, 2014; 4(3): 159-65.

57. A. Gupta, J.S.Yadav, S.Rawat, etal., Method development and hydrolytic degradation study of Doxofylline by RPHPLC and LC– MS/MS, AsianJ. Pharm. Anal, 2011; 1: 14–18.
58. G. Boccardi, Oxidative susceptibility testing, in: S.W. Baertschi (Ed.), Pharmaceutical Stress Testing-Predicting Drug Degradation, Taylor and Francis, New York, 2005; 220.
59. R. M. Patel, P. M. Patel and N. M. Patel, Stability indicating method development- A Review. International Research Journal of Pharmacy, 2011; 2(5): 79-87.
60. C. Wen, Desiging HPLC Methods for Stability Indication and Forced Degradation Sample for API, Americon Pharmaceutical Review.
61. S. P. Biradar, T. M. Kalyankar, S. J. Wadher, R. S. Moon and S. S. Dange, Stability Indicating HPLC Method Development: Review. Asian Journal of Medicinal and Analytical Chemistry, 2014; 01(01): 21-26.
62. J. W. Dolan: Stability Indicating assay. LC Troubleshooting LCGC North America, 2005; 275.
63. V. Gupta, A. D. Jain, N. S. Gill, K. Gupta, Development and validation of HPLC method - A review. International Research Journal of Pharmaceutical and Applied Sciences, 2012; 2(4): 17-25.
64. U. Deokate, S. Syed, F. khan, A Stability indicating HPLC method for the determination of Mepivacaine Hydrochloride. International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2013; 5(3): 941-947.
65. Shah BP, Jain S, Prajapati KK, Mansuri NY. Stability indicating HPLC method development: A Review. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, 2012 Sep 1; 3(9): 2978.
66. Wypych G, editor. Handbook of UV degradation and stabilization. Elsevier; 2020 Mar 9.
67. Alsante KM, Ando A, Brown R, Ensing J, Hatajik TD, Kong W, Tsuda Y. The role of degradant profiling in active pharmaceutical ingredients and drug products, Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev., 2007; 59(1): 29-37.
68. Alsante K, Ahuja S. Handbook of Isolation and Characterization of Impurities in Pharmaceutical, Academics Press, New York, Solving impurity/degradation problems: case studies, 2003; 380.
69. BK, Kizzie AC.Forced Degradation to Develop Stabilityindicating Methods. American Pharmaceutical Review, 2007; 10(6): 1-14.
70. Singh S, Bakshi M. Guidance on Conduct of Stress Tests to Determine Inherent Stability of Drugs. Pharmaceutical Technology, 2000; 1-14.

71. Update on the WHO Stability Guideline Book. (2010) Pharmaceutical Stability Testing to Support Global Markets Publisher: Springer New York Copyright.
72. FDA guidance for industry method validation. (2001). US Department of Health and Human Services. Food and Drug Administration. Centre for Drug Evaluation and Research CDER.
73. Roberto de Alvarenga Junior B, Lajarim Carneiro R. Chemometrics approaches in forced degradation studies of pharmaceutical drugs. *Molecules*, 2019 Oct 22; 24(20): 3804.
74. Torres S, Brown R, Szucs R, Hawkins JM, Zelesky T, Scrivens G, Pettman A, Taylor MR. The application of electrochemistry to pharmaceutical stability testing—Comparison with in silico prediction and chemical forced degradation approaches. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 2015 Nov 10; 115: 487-501.
75. Salunkhe MN, Gite SD, Kachave RN. Recent trends in impurity profiling and forced degradation of antihypertensive drugs. *Journal of Liquid Chromatography & Related Technologies*, 2017 Oct 2; 40(16): 813-31.